

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN LEADERSHIP STYLES, TEACHER ENGAGEMENT, AND JOB SATISFACTION: AN ASSESSMENT

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ABSTRACT

Leadership establishes the tone for the workplace culture, which shapes the employees' engagement and satisfaction with the organization. Hence, this study assessed the relationship between the leadership style, teacher engagement, and job satisfaction of secondary school administrators and teachers in the District of Jiabong, Schools Division of Samar, during the School Year 2024-2025. Based on the findings, while the school administrator-respondents perceived themselves as always practicing transformational, transactional, and innovative leadership styles, the teacher-respondents had considered them only often practiced. Meanwhile, the school administrator-respondents and the teacher-respondents considered the teacher engagement as only often practiced. Moreover, both respondents viewed the teachers' job satisfaction as often practiced. There were significant differences in the perceptions between the school administrator- and teacher-respondents as to the leadership styles and teacher engagement, while there were none as to the job satisfaction of teachers. The school administrator-respondents' sex, number of years as school administrator, and attitude toward leadership styles, teacher engagement, and job satisfaction were significantly related to their leadership styles. Finally, the school administrator-respondents' leadership styles and teacher engagement and job satisfaction of teacher-respondents were significantly related.

Keywords: *Leadership styles, teacher engagement, job satisfaction, school administrators, teachers*

INTRODUCTION

Leadership establishes the tone for workplace culture, which significantly shapes employees' engagement and satisfaction within the organization. This management function of leadership is fundamental to any organization because it fosters open communication, provides clear instructions, and acknowledges employee contributions (Duran, 2025; Cumar et al., 2025). By establishing effective leadership, employees feel appreciated and empowered to contribute meaningfully, resulting in higher engagement and job satisfaction. However, leaders typically display a variety of leadership styles as they inspire and motivate their followers. These leadership styles have unique impacts on how leaders create an environment conducive to engagement and satisfaction (Bellibaş et al., 2025). The challenge of leadership is even more pronounced in educational organizations, where expectations for the effective delivery of functions are multisectoral and complex.

While all organizations require leadership, modern societies have raised expectations for schools. The evolution of school systems to meet societal demands underlies the shifting expectations of school leaders. School leadership is defined as the process of directing and influencing a school community toward achieving educational goals by establishing vision, allocating resources, fostering collaboration, and nurturing a positive school culture (Harris & Jones, 2023; Abid et al., 2025). Corollary to this, a school leader occupies a key leadership role in a school and is responsible for establishing the mission, overseeing daily operations, and promoting constructive change in the learning environment, including the professional development of teachers, student outcomes, and school culture.

High-quality education relies heavily on effective leadership. Research indicates that educational leadership is among the most critical factors influencing learning outcomes (Adeoye, 2025). Globally, school leaders, particularly principals, are expected to formulate their schools' philosophy. In Canada, principals play a vital role in setting and adjusting high-performance expectations within a results-based management framework. In Hong Kong and China, principals shape their schools' vision and mission according to global trends and adopt a system-thinking approach. In Japan, principals align school vision with national, prefectural, and municipal education policies. The 2024 Global Education Monitoring Report (GEM) emphasizes that beyond establishing a school's philosophy, leaders must also design curricula, observe teaching practices and provide feedback, and foster professional collaboration among teachers (Broadley, 2024).

The effectiveness of school leadership depends largely on the leadership styles employed. Leadership styles are the behaviors and methods leaders use to motivate subordinates toward organizational objectives (Ogunode et al., 2023; Siburian, 2025). These styles may emphasize tasks, relationships, or a combination, depending on the

leader's approach. School administrators adopt different leadership styles according to school circumstances, using them to address pressing educational challenges. Understanding these variations is crucial to providing appropriate support for teachers' well-being, job satisfaction, and engagement (Kauppila, 2024; Duran, 2025).

Leadership styles can serve as strategic tools for achieving organizational objectives by fostering teacher engagement and satisfaction. Teacher engagement reflects the energy, passion, and meaningful participation teachers bring to their roles, encompassing emotional, cognitive, and physical commitment. Job satisfaction refers to the level of contentment teachers experience in their work, a key factor influencing overall well-being and motivation (Cumar et al., 2025; Bellibaş et al., 2025). Studies indicate that teachers who witness effective leadership, leaders who encourage excellence and model supportive behaviors, tend to demonstrate higher levels of engagement and satisfaction (Kauppila, 2024; Abid et al., 2025).

At the local level, leadership in Philippine schools was institutionalized through Republic Act No. 9155, or the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, which empowered schools to make decisions for the benefit of learners. This law strengthened school-based management (SBM), particularly the role of principals, enabling them to make critical decisions affecting teachers, students, parents, and other stakeholders. By decentralizing authority, principals can take initiatives to improve teacher welfare and school outcomes (Rivera & Ibarra, 2020).

School administrators' leadership styles are central to fostering teacher development within the SBM framework, including addressing individual needs, promoting engagement, and guiding professional development initiatives. However, systemic challenges such as political instability, resource limitations, large class sizes, language barriers, and inadequate infrastructure often constrain administrators' ability to practice effective leadership (Macapobre et al., 2024). These interconnected challenges affect leadership styles, teacher engagement, and satisfaction.

Local studies highlight that administrators in the Schools Division of Samar exhibited high leadership levels in five key result areas of the Office Performance Commitment Review Form (OPCRF), with scores approaching the maximum in instructional leadership, learning environment, human resource management, operations, and community partnership (Cebiano, 2020). Nonetheless, qualitative findings revealed challenges, such as overlapping responsibilities and scheduling conflicts, that limited the optimization of leadership practices to enhance teacher engagement and satisfaction. In the District of Jiabong, the OPCRf rating indicated very satisfactory performance (average 4.43), but SBM implementation remained low (0.39), underscoring the need for evidence-based strategies to link leadership styles with teacher outcomes.

This study, therefore, seeks to generate research-based data on the relationships among school administrators' leadership styles and teachers' job engagement and satisfaction. The findings aim to contribute to the literature on leadership in education

and provide input for developing a leadership enhancement program in the District of Jiabong, Schools Division of Samar.

Research Questions

This study assessed the relationship between the leadership style, teacher engagement, and job satisfaction of secondary school administrators and teachers in the District of Jiabong, Schools Division of Samar, during the School Year 2024-2025.

Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the school administrator-respondents in terms of the following variates:
 - 1.1 age and sex;
 - 1.2 civil status;
 - 1.3 gross monthly family income;
 - 1.4 highest educational attainment;
 - 1.5 number of years as school administrators;
 - 1.6 school administrative position;
 - 1.7 number of relevant in-service trainings;
 - 1.8 performance rating based on the latest OPCRF; and
 - 1.9 attitude toward leadership styles, job engagement, and job satisfaction?
2. What is the profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of the following variates:
 - 2.1 age and sex;
 - 2.2 civil status;
 - 2.3 gross monthly family income;
 - 2.4 highest educational attainment;
 - 2.5 number of years in teaching;
 - 2.6 teaching position;
 - 2.7 number of relevant in-service trainings;
 - 2.8 performance rating based on the latest IPCRF; and
 - 2.9 attitude toward leadership styles, teacher engagement, and job satisfaction?
3. What is the level of leadership style exhibited by the school administrator-respondents as perceived by themselves and the teacher-respondents in terms of the following leadership styles:
 - 3.1 transformational leadership;
 - 3.2 transactional leadership; and
 - 3.3 innovative leadership?
4. What is the teacher engagement level of the teacher-respondents as perceived by themselves and the school administrator-respondents in terms of the following dimensions:
 - 4.1 emotional engagement;
 - 4.2 cognitive engagement; and
 - 4.3 behavioral engagement?

5. What is the job satisfaction level of the teacher-respondents as perceived by themselves and the school administrator-respondents in terms of the following factors:
 - 5.1 motivation factors; and
 - 5.2 hygiene factors?
6. Is there a significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents as regards to the leadership styles of the school administrators, and teacher engagement and job satisfaction of teachers?
7. Is there a significant relationship between the leadership styles of the school administrator-respondents and the following variates:
 - 7.1 school administrator-related variates;
 - 7.2 level of teacher engagement; and
 - 7.2 level of job satisfaction?
8. What intervention program may be proposed based on the findings of the study?

Locale of the Study

Figure 1 shows the map of the study locale, the secondary schools in the District of Jiabong, Schools Division of Samar.

The study focused on three public secondary schools located within the District of Jiabong: Jiabong National High School (JNHS), Cuyting Uy National High School, and Casapa National High School.

These schools serve as key educational institutions in the area, each contributing to the educational development of the municipality and surrounding communities.

Jiabong became an independent municipality on October 22, 1948, when Congress approved House Bill No. 1812, which was enacted into law under Republic Act No. 269.

Education in Jiabong has evolved to meet the needs of its growing population. The municipality is home to three public secondary schools, each located in different barangays: Poblacion, Malino, and Casapa. Jiabong National High School (JNHS), founded in 1994, is located in Poblacion and serves as the main educational institution in the area.

JNHS caters to students from various barangays, including those from more rural areas, and has long been a central hub for secondary education in Jiabong. As the population continued to grow, there was a pressing need to establish additional schools to accommodate the increasing number of students. This led to the establishment of Cuyting Uy National High School and Casapa National High School in 2014.

Figure 1

The Map Showing the Locale of the Study

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a quantitative descriptive–correlational, and comparative research design to determine the relationship among leadership styles, teacher engagement, and job satisfaction of school administrators and teachers in the three public secondary schools in the District of Jiabong, Schools Division of Samar, during the School Year 2024–2025. A total enumeration sampling technique was employed, involving 11 school administrators and 100 teachers as respondents. Standardized questionnaires adopted from previous studies and validated through expert review were used to gather data, employing a five-point Likert scale. After securing the necessary approvals, the researcher personally administered and collected the questionnaires while ensuring confidentiality and anonymity of responses. The collected data were encoded and analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), applying frequency count, percentage, mean, weighted mean, independent samples t-test, Spearman's rho, Chi-square test, Cramer's V, Fisher's Exact Test, and Shapiro–Wilk test for normality, with the level of significance set at 0.05 for hypothesis testing.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following were the salient findings of the study:

1. The majority of school administrators in this group were 47 years old or older, representing nearly half of the respondents or 45.45 percent. The next largest group of school administrator-respondents were aged 37 to 41, with 36.36 percent of those surveyed. However, a smaller portion of the school administrator-respondents, about 18.18 percent, were between 42 and 46 years old. The mean age of all school administrator-respondents was 48.18 years, with a median age of 45. The ages varied by about 8.0164 years on average. Meanwhile, the female school-administrator-respondents at six out of 11 outnumbered the male school administrator-respondents at five in this sample.

2. Over half of the total school administrator-respondents in this study were married at six or 54.55 percent. The next largest group was comprised of single teachers that represented about four or 36.36 percent of the responses. However, one or 9.09 percent school administrator-respondent was separated.

3. A majority of the school administrator-respondents, eight or 72.73 percent, reported a gross monthly family income of Php 45,000 or more, which also indicated the highest income earned for this group. This was followed by two or 18.18 percent with gross monthly family income of Php 40,000 – 44,999 and one or 9.09 percent who reported the lowest gross monthly family income at Php 25,000 – 29,999.

4. An equal number of four or 36.36 percent of the 11 total school administrator-respondents reported they had master's degree and with their master's degree units. Moreover, there were three or 27.27 percent school administrator-respondents who had

the highest level of education attained with doctorate degree.

5. There was nearly half at five or 45.45 percent of the total 11 school administrator-respondents, who had between six and 10 years of experience as school administrators. The remaining number of school administrator-respondents were fairly evenly distributed across other experience levels, with an equal number at two or 18.18 percent who had 16-20 years of administrative experience, 11-15 years, and less than one to five years of administrative experience.

6. Six or 54.55 percent of the 11-school administrator-respondents held the Head Teacher I position. Yet, there were two or 18.18 percent school administrator-respondents who occupied the Head Teacher II position. An equal number at one or 9.09 percent held Head Teacher I, School Principal I and III positions.

7. At the district level, majority of school administrator-respondents or seven or 63.64 percent participated in only one district-level relevant in-service training. Yet, this was followed by an equal number at two or 18.18 school administrator-respondents who attended two to three relevant in-service trainings. The most common number of division-level relevant in-service trainings among the school administrator-respondents was either one or two, with each of these quantities representing four or 36.36 percent of the school administrator-respondents. The most common number of regional-level relevant in-service trainings attended by the school administrator-respondents was three, with about four or 36.36 percent of the total 11 school administrator-respondents. Yet, three or 27.27 percent school administrator-respondents had attended one relevant in-service regional-level training, which was considered the least number of in-service trainings attended. More so, one or 9.09 percent school administrator-respondent had the greatest number of regional in-service trainings attended at six. A higher number of school administrator-respondents at four or 36.36 percent out of 11 attended five relevant in-service trainings at the national level. There was one or 9.09 percent school administrator-respondent who attended the greatest number of relevant in-service trainings at the national level at eight, while there were two or 18.18 who attended the least number of relevant in-service training at the national level at one. There was one or 9.09 percent school administrator-respondent who attended the greatest number of relevant in-service trainings at the international level with 10 trainings. An equal number of school administrator-respondents at three or 27.27 percent had attended six and five relevant in-service trainings at the international level. However, there were two or 18.18 percent of the school administrator-respondents who attended the least number of relevant in-service training at one.

8. An overwhelming majority of the school administrator-respondents or 10 or 90.91 percent of the 11 showed an outstanding performance based on their OPCRf ratings between 4.50 and 5.00.

9. The overall attitude of school administrator-respondents toward leadership style was highly positive, with a grand weighted mean of 4.72, indicating that they "always" employed positive leadership practices. Several specific leadership behaviors received

high ratings at 4.73, also interpreted as always for adapting leadership styles to different situations, staff needs, and student outcomes; demonstrating personal leadership through interactions with colleagues; communicating a clear leadership vision and approach; fostering innovation and risk-taking among teachers; and encouraging two-way feedback between teachers and administrators. There was, however, one statement on the inclusivity in decision-making and recognizing diverse perspectives among staff, which earned a weighted mean of 4.64. The school administrator-respondents demonstrated a consistently positive attitude toward teacher engagement, with a grand weighted mean of 4.58, indicating they always engaged in practices that promote teacher engagement. The highest-rated practices were providing access to professional growth opportunities and fostering collaborative expertise among teachers, with a weighted mean of 4.64. Moreover, other statement indicators of the attitude toward teacher engagement had a weighted mean of 4.55 for encouraging teacher involvement in school governance and policy implementation; acknowledging and appreciating teacher efforts and achievements; ensuring a positive and safe school culture that fosters engagement; clarifying communication regarding expectations and goals; and aligning teachers' personal beliefs and values with the school's mission and vision. The school administrator-respondents expressed a positive overall attitude toward job satisfaction, with a grand weighted mean of 4.54, interpreted as always. This indicated that the school administrator-respondents were satisfied with their administrative jobs. Several factors contributed strongly to this positive perception based on the weighted mean of 4.55, interpreted as always for: satisfaction with salary, benefits, and fair treatment; support from administrators in their roles and responsibilities; opportunities for career growth and advancement; a conducive working atmosphere characterized by collegiality, respect, and shared goals; respect for teachers' autonomy in choosing teaching methods and curricula; and the ability to maintain a healthy work-life balance.

10. The largest group of teacher-respondents were aged 27-31 years old with 29 or 29 percent of the total 100 teacher-respondents, which was closely followed by those aged 32 to 36 with 25 or 25 percent. The mean age of the teachers surveyed was 36.08 years, with a median age of 35, indicating a relatively symmetrical age distribution. The ages typically varied by about 6.6276 years. A significantly higher number of female teacher-respondents at 64 compared to the male teacher-respondents at 36.

11. Majority of the teacher-respondents or 71 or 71.00 percent were married, while 28 or 28 percent were single. However, there was one or one percent teacher-respondent who was widowed.

12. There were 48 or 48 percent of the teacher-respondents had a gross monthly family income of Php 30,000 – 34,999, followed by 29 or 29 percent who had gross monthly family income of Php 25,000 – 29,999. There was, however, one or one percent who indicated the highest gross monthly family income at Php 45,000 and above, while three or three percent indicated the lowest gross monthly family income at Php 10,000-14,999.

13. A large majority of the teacher-respondents at 85 out of 100 or 85 percent pursued graduate studies inasmuch as they indicated that they had earned units in their master's degree programs. This was followed by 10 of the 100 teacher-respondents or about 10 percent graduated from their master's degrees. Additionally, two or about two percent of the teacher-respondents had indicated the highest educational level by the units earned in their doctorate degree programs. There were still three or three percent teacher-respondents with their baccalaureate degrees only.

14. Almost half of the teacher-respondents or 49 out of 100 or 49 percent had been teaching for 6-10 years, representing the largest group in terms of experience. This was followed by 37 or 37 percent teacher-respondents who had less than five years of teaching experience, which was also indicated as the shortest teaching experience for this study. Yet, there was one out of the 100 teacher-respondents or approximately one percent who had the longest years spent in teaching at 26-30 years.

15. The most common position held by teacher-respondents was Teacher III, with 40 out of the 100 total teacher-respondents or about 40 percent. This was followed by the Teacher II position with 37 or 37 percent teacher-respondents and Teacher 1 with 18 or 18 percent. Among the 100 teacher-respondents, there were five or five percent which indicated the highest academic ranking as Master Teacher I.

16. The majority of teacher-respondents or about 65 out of 100 or 65 percent participated in one to three district-level relevant in-service trainings, which was also identified as the least number of relevant in-service trainings attended. Yet, 13 or 13 percent teacher-respondents had the most relevant in-service trainings attended at 10 and above, and 20 or 20 percent which was the second largest group of teacher-respondents who attended moderate number of relevant in-service trainings at 4-6. A large majority of the teacher-respondents or 72 or 72 percent who participated in 1-3 relevant in-service trainings at the division level, followed by 20 or 20 percent who had 4-6 trainings. However, one or one percent indicated the greatest number of relevant in-service trainings at 10 and above, while there were six or six percent who indicated non-attendance in division level. The most common number of regional-level relevant in-service trainings completed by teacher-respondents is one, representing about 46 out of 100 teacher-respondents or 46 percent of the group. This was followed by 20 or 20 percent teacher-respondents who attended about two relevant in-service trainings at the regional level, and 12 or 12 percent who had three. However, there were 16 or 16 percent out of 100 teacher-respondents who did not have a chance to attend any relevant in-service trainings at the regional level, while one or one percent teacher-respondent attended the greatest number of relevant in-service trainings at the regional level at five. Almost half of the teacher-respondents or about 45 out of the 100 sampled or 45 percent had not participated in any national-level relevant in-service trainings. However, there were 35 or 35 percent teacher-respondents who were given the opportunity to attend one relevant in-service training at the national level. There were five or about five percent of the teacher-respondents had the opportunity to attend as many as three relevant in-service trainings at the national level. An overwhelming majority of the teacher-respondents or about 94 or 94 percent had not participated in

any international-level relevant in-service trainings.

17. A substantial majority of the teacher-respondents at 71 or 71 percent who earned an IPCRF rating of 4.50-5.00, which was considered as outstanding performance. However, the remaining 29 or 29 percent of out of the 100 teacher-respondents earned an IPCRF rating of 3.50 - 4.49, which was considered as very satisfactory performance.

18. The teacher-respondents generally viewed their school administrators' leadership styles positively based on the grand weighted mean of 4.28, which indicated that they "often" agreed with the positive statements about their school administrators' leadership. Of the aspects rated as "often", the most highly rated with a weighed mean of 4.49 was the administrator's communication of their leadership vision and approach. However, the lowest rated aspect with a weighted mean of 3.97 was the administrator's willingness to adapt their leadership style based on context, staff needs, and student outcomes. The teacher-respondents had a positive view of their school administrators' efforts toward teacher engagement based on the value of the grand weighted mean at 4.32, indicating further that these efforts were "often" observed. It was also found that the most appreciated aspect of school administrators' support was the encouragement of teacher involvement in school governance and policy implementation based on the weighted mean of 4.42. Yet, the teacher-respondents' considered the initiation of collaborative expertise among teachers within their teams or departments as the lowest-rated area of support provided by the school administrators based on the weighted mean of 4.25. The teacher-respondents generally reported a positive job satisfaction, with an overall weighted mean of 4.36 indicating they "often" felt satisfied. Two key factors stood out as contributing most strongly to this positive perception based on the value of the weighted mean at 4.39: a conducive working environment characterized by collegiality, respect, and shared goals, and ability to maintain a healthy work-life balance. However, the area perceived as needing the most improvement based on the value of the weighted mean at 4.25 related to workload balance and fairness in the distribution of responsibilities.

19. The school administrator-respondents perceived themselves as consistently demonstrating transformational leadership qualities, with a grand weighted mean of 4.56, which indicated that they always exhibited such style of leadership. They particularly saw themselves as strong in motivating staff through passion and enthusiasm for school improvement, actively supporting teacher professional development, and fostering a collaborative environment based on the weighted mean at 4.64. The teacher-respondents perceived the level of transformational leadership by their school administrators as often practiced based on the value of the weighted mean at 4.22. The teacher-respondents particularly appreciated the feeling of being inspired by the principal's vision as shown by the weighted mean of 4.27 and trusting the principal's decisions to benefit both the students and the teachers based on the weighted mean of 4.27. However, the lowest-rated aspect of transformational leadership with a weighted mean of 4.13 was the feeling of empowerment to make decisions within their own classrooms.

20. The school administrator-respondents perceived themselves as consistently exhibiting transactional leadership behaviors based on a grand weighted mean of 4.62, indicating that these behaviors were always present. Specifically, it was revealed that they rated themselves highly in providing clear instructions and expectations, rewarding teachers for meeting expectations, closely monitoring performance, emphasizing order and discipline, establishing clear rules and guidelines, and providing structured feedback based on the value of the weighted at 4.64. While still perceived as always present, the lowest-rated transactional leadership behaviors were enforcing consequences for not following directives and focusing on short-term goals with a weighted mean value of 4.55. The teacher-respondents generally perceived their school administrators as exhibiting transactional leadership based on the weighted mean of 4.32. It was likewise shown that the most appreciated aspect by the teacher-respondents as regards to the transactional leadership styles exhibited by their school administrators was clarity of expectations set by the principal with a weighted mean of 4.49. However, the lowest-rated aspect as shown by the value of the weighted mean at 4.20 was gaining rewards for meeting expectations.

21. The school administrator-respondents perceived themselves as consistently demonstrating innovative leadership based on a grand weighted mean of 4.73, indicating that they always exhibited such leadership. Remarkably, every measured aspect of innovative leadership received the same high rating of 4.73. These aspects included encouraging experimentation with new teaching methods, supporting teachers who try creative ideas, valuing innovation, fostering an environment where new ideas are welcomed, challenging the status quo, exploring unconventional solutions, taking calculated risks, and encouraging staff to think outside the box. The teacher-respondents generally perceived their school administrators as demonstrating innovative leadership based on the overall weighted mean of 4.27, which suggested that these qualities were often observed. The finding specifically shows that the teacher-respondents particularly appreciated the principal's willingness to take calculated risks for school improvement based on a weighted mean of 4.35. However, the lowest-rated aspect of innovative leadership as shown by the weighted mean of 4.20 was for the encouragement to experiment with new teaching methods.

22. The school administrator-respondents perceived the teachers as emotionally engaged based on the overall weighted mean of 3.97, which indicated that the dimensions of emotional engagement by the teachers were often observed by the school administrator-respondents. Specifically, the school administrator-respondents considered the teachers as connected to their colleagues and the school environment based on the weighted mean of 4.27. However, enthusiasm for coming to work each day was perceived as less frequent with a weighted mean of 3.64, suggesting that this aspect of the teachers' emotional engagement could be an area for focus and improvement. The teacher-respondents perceived themselves as highly emotionally engaged based on the grand weighted mean of 4.49. They specifically emphasized strongly their deep care for student success and well-being as shown by the weighted mean of 4.70. However, the perceived emotional connection to colleagues and school environment was slightly lower based on the weighted mean at 4.28.

23. The school administrator-respondents considered their teachers as cognitively engaged across all areas based on the grand weighted mean of 4.20, which further indicated that the indicators were often observed. The table further shows that of the indicators of the teachers' cognitive engagement, the school administrator-respondents considered the teachers' commitment to professional growth and development as highly observed based on the value of the weighted mean at 4.45. However, they observed less frequent application of professional development learning in classroom practice based on the weighted mean of 3.82. The teacher-respondents considered themselves as highly cognitively engaged at work based on the overall weighted mean of 4.46, which indicated that they often showed the parameters of cognitive engagement. They particularly emphasized constant pursuit of improved teaching practices as shown by the weighted mean of 4.57. While still positive, the perceived intellectual stimulation derived from their work was slightly lower with a weighed mean of 4.38.

24. The school administrator-respondents considered the teachers as behaviorally engaged at work based on the grand weighted mean of 4.24, which further indicated that the dimensions of behavioral engagement were observed among the teachers. The school administrator-respondents particularly placed value on the teachers' contributions to extracurricular programs and events as well as their efforts to build strong relationships with students, parents, and their colleagues based on the value of the weighted mean at 4.45. However, several aspects of behavioral engagement by teachers received slightly lower ratings of 4.09: active participation in school activities beyond teaching duties, volunteering for committees or initiatives, willingness to go beyond basic duties, and regular attendance and participation in school meetings and professional development. The teacher-respondents generally viewed themselves as highly behaviorally engaged based on the overall weighted mean of 4.47, which indicated that they often demonstrated the parameters of this type of engagement. The table particularly shows that the teacher-respondents valued their regular attendance and participation in school meetings and professional development based on the weighted mean of 4.68. While still positive, their perceived level of collaboration with colleagues was slightly lower based on the weighted mean of 4.37.

25. The school administrator-respondents generally perceived teachers as satisfied with the motivational aspects of their jobs, with a grand weighted mean of 4.25 indicating these factors are "often" present. It was also found that the school administrator-respondents observed fulfillment by teachers derived from their relationships with students and colleagues, as well as a sense of job security, both with a weighted mean of 4.55. However, the teachers' satisfaction with their salary and benefits was given by the school administrator-respondents with a lower value of 3.82. The teacher-respondents considered themselves as satisfied with the motivational factors in their jobs, with an overall weighted mean of 4.33 indicating that these factors were often present. Of these motivation factors, job security was considered by the teacher-respondents as a strong motivator in their jobs based on the weighted mean of 4.59. However, the teacher-respondents' satisfaction with their salary and benefits obtained a lower weighted mean of 4.06.

26. The school administrator-respondents perceived their teachers as satisfied with hygiene factors, with an overall weighted mean of 4.16 indicating that these factors were often considered. It was also specifically shown that the school administrator-respondents placed a high value on the availability of essential teaching materials and resources based on the weighted mean of 4.45. However, the lowest-rated aspects with a weighted mean of 3.91 were for the cleanliness, lighting, and ventilation of classrooms, and teachers' comfort within their workspaces. The teacher-respondents considered themselves satisfied with respect to hygiene factors in their work environment, with an overall weighted mean of 4.33 indicating these factors were often present. The teacher-respondents considered themselves particularly satisfied with working in clean, well-lit, and adequately ventilated classrooms based on the highest weighted mean of 4.52, which was interpreted as always. However, the lowest-rated aspect with a weighted mean of 4.23 was the receipt of meaningful feedback that helps them improve their teaching.

27. The null hypothesis that posited no difference in the perceptions between the school administrator- and teacher-respondents with regard to the level of leadership styles by the school administrators, was rejected due to a low p-value (0.011) falling below the established significance level of 0.05. The calculated t-value (-2.599) further supported this conclusion.

28. The statistical analysis indicated a significant difference in how school administrator-respondents and teacher-respondents perceived the teacher engagement level. The null hypothesis, stating no difference in these perceptions, was rejected due to a low p-value of 0.005, which was less than the significance level of 0.05. The t-value of 2.845 further supported this rejection.

29. The null hypothesis, which stated that there was no significant difference in the perceptions between the school administrator-respondents and teacher-respondents as regards to the job satisfaction level of the teachers, was accepted because the computed p-value of 0.463 was considerably higher than the significance level of 0.05. The t-value of 0.736 further supported the acceptance.

30. The school administrator-respondents' sex, number of years as a school administrator, and attitudes toward leadership styles had significant relationships with their perceived leadership styles. The strongest correlation was found between the sex and perceived leadership style of the school administrator-respondents with a p-value of 0.040 and a Cramer's V of 0.869. A negatively strong correlation existed between the number of years as a school administrator and perceived leadership style of the school administrator-respondents based on the p-value of 0.028 and a Spearman's rho of -0.658. Finally, a strong positive correlation was found between the attitudes toward leadership styles, teacher engagement, and job satisfaction, and the perceived leadership styles of the school administrator-respondents based on the p-value of 0.011 and Spearman's rho of 0.729.

31. A strong, positive relationship between school administrator-respondents'

leadership styles and the level of teacher engagement, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis which stated that no such relationship existed. The statistical significance of this finding was underscored by a p-value of 0.010, well below the 0.05 significance level, and further reinforced by a strong Spearman rho correlation coefficient of 0.737.

32. A strong, positive correlation existed between the leadership styles of the school administrator-respondents and the level of job satisfaction of teachers, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis which stated that there was no relationship between these two variables. The low p-value of 0.015, which was less than the significance level of 0.05, confirmed the statistical significance of this finding. This strong relationship was further supported by a Spearman rho value of 0.708.

Conclusions

The findings revealed that both school administrators and teachers demonstrated high levels of performance, positive attitudes, and overall job satisfaction; however, significant perception gaps existed between the two groups regarding leadership styles and teacher engagement. School administrators tended to rate their transformational, transactional, and innovative leadership behaviors more highly than teachers did, particularly in areas of empowerment, rewards, innovation support, and meaningful feedback. While both groups generally agreed on the level of teacher job satisfaction, especially regarding motivation and hygiene factors, salary and benefits and the need for constructive feedback remained common concerns. Notably, leadership styles were significantly related to certain administrator profile variables and showed strong positive relationships with both teacher engagement and job satisfaction, underscoring the critical role of effective leadership in fostering an engaged and satisfied teaching workforce. Overall, the study highlighted the need for school administrators to strengthen feedback mechanisms, enhance teacher empowerment, align perceptions through open communication, and actively support professional growth to bridge existing gaps and promote a more collaborative and supportive school environment.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, it is recommended that school administrators undergo customized and continuous leadership development programs that consider gender, years of administrative experience, and attitudes toward leadership, engagement, and job satisfaction, while expanding access to regional, national, and international trainings to strengthen adaptive leadership competencies. Schools should enhance communication and structured feedback mechanisms to bridge perception gaps, promote teacher empowerment, and improve recognition and reward systems. Administrators are encouraged to provide meaningful opportunities for teacher involvement in decision-making processes, such as active participation and facilitation in School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) sessions, while addressing immediate workplace concerns and advocating for long-term welfare support. Furthermore, the Department of Education (DepEd) should refine its leadership training frameworks, formulate

responsive policies on teacher welfare, and guide school heads in implementing strategies that improve engagement and retention. Finally, future studies may explore the effectiveness of specific leadership styles across varied educational contexts to further strengthen evidence-based leadership practices.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study strictly adhered to established ethical standards in the conduct of research. Prior to data collection, formal permission was secured from the Schools Division Office and the respective school heads. Participation of the school administrators and teachers was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained after clearly explaining the purpose, procedures, and significance of the study. The respondents were assured of confidentiality and anonymity, and no identifying information was disclosed in any part of the report. The data gathered were used solely for academic and research purposes and were handled with utmost care to ensure privacy and integrity. Furthermore, the study avoided any form of coercion, bias, or misrepresentation, and all findings were reported honestly and accurately in accordance with ethical research principles.

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